

Significance of Related Learning Experience Towards Competent Nursing Work Performance

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Abstract:

Related Learning Experience (RLE) is a major and vital aspect of the nursing curriculum. It is where students are molded and trained to be competent, effective and efficient future nurses. It is also where teamwork and collaboration with the health team is developed and honed. From clinical practice in the hospitals, clinics and communities, significant learnings can create challenges in handling new environments, diverse patients, demanding classmates and clinical instructors; but all these are consequential for nursing students' competency and training in critical and problem-solving techniques. This study investigated the nursing students' perceptions on the impact of clinical learning experience that contributed to

competent nursing work performance. Online questionnaires were administered to one hundred (100) respondents. Quantitative content analysis was used to analyze the data. Results of the study indicated that having sufficient, efficient and meaningful clinical practice as undergraduates can propel them to successful work competencies and job placement. Results of the study revolved on areas of clinical efficiency, critical thinking, problem-solving and social-moral support provided by academically qualified, and competent clinical instructors were factors contributing to creating skilled nurses who show genuine care about their patients, performing work with great efficiency, and caring with empathy and compassion.

Keywords: *Related Learning Experience, Clinical Efficiency, Critical Thinking Skills, Empathy, Compassionate Care, Teamwork.*

Introduction

Related Learning Experience (RLE) is a teaching-learning strategy designed to enhance and improve the competencies of nursing students by deploying them to hospitals, clinics and communities utilizing methods in various health scenarios. Clinical learning is an important element of nursing education that can support the development of competence.

Nursing students have expectations for their clinical learning that should be satisfied accordingly by providing enriching clinical

experiences to their great advantage in terms of efficiency, competence and confidence in handling varied types of patients in their future employment as professional nurses.

This study utilized the descriptive research design to obtain information from the results of the research questionnaire formulated by the author to find out the perceptions of BSN students on their RLE. The students were from second year to fourth year of St. Mary's College of Baliuag, Inc. during the AY 2023-2024. The students, in their RLE, were expected to enrich

their nursing knowledge, skills and attitudes through blended instruction utilizing lectures, skills laboratory, conferences, seminars, and webinars with contemporary interactions employing games and Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education. Clinical experience helps nursing students become accustomed to high-stress moments as they are taught to learn efficiently through self-directed learning that will hone their preparation skills and reflexes to overcome challenges in hospitals with maximum tolerance and confidence.

Colindres et al. (2019) highly recommends enhancing the nursing students' skills through RLE to guarantee and sustain competent nursing work performance.

Consequently, when nursing students were interviewed after their clinical immersion in hospitals, they considered most valuable the enriching clinical experience of taking care of patients with the supervision of competent clinical instructors. They found the clinical experience most encouraging to learn time management, listening and communication skills.

As proven in one research done, the quality of clinical mentoring and learning environments are sources of nursing students' positive experiences from their Related Learning Experiences. The motivating leadership of efficient clinical instructors may strengthen clinical experience as a learning environment for the nursing students. (Jacobsen et al. 2022).

Resulting from the study conducted by Zhou, et al. (2024), male nursing students' experiences from their clinical internships described difficulties and challenges in physical and mental well-being when working in hospitals. There has been a gradual increase in the percentage of male nursing students in recent years from its traditionally dominant profession for women. Gender sensitivity issues and balance between strength and weaknesses should be practiced in training and handling male nursing students in the clinical areas whether in the hospitals, clinics and communities.

A good nurse who shows empathy for every patient, treats patients as individuals, focusing on

a person-centered care approach rather than strictly following routines and guidelines. Critical thinking and problem-solving skills are essentials to nursing, as they render a one-on-one time with patients and make decisions about health issues concerning their nursing care. It is also necessary for nurses to possess solid analytical skills to collect information, evaluate the facts, and develop a rational conclusion to improve patient outcomes. (ANA Nursing Resources Hub, 2023)

Bedside learning has been identified as a crucial part of developing a professional registered nurse. Akram (2018) writes, "Clinical learning is a key area that explicates the importance of nursing students' performance in the clinical setting and provides them an avenue to practice their skills, develop their professional identity, increase their knowledge, and apply the theoretical and practical knowledge in the clinical setting" as cited by Betzen (2024).

The findings of the study highly recommend enhancing nursing students' skills through RLE that would make them competent in their work experience. Naturally, provision of quality nursing education coupled with enriched clinical experience provided by academically qualified instructors can boost the moral confidence of the nursing students to strive for excellence.

Objective of the Study

This study aims to explore nursing students' expectations and experiences from their clinical exposures to intensify their understanding of the nursing theories and concepts learned from the classroom.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized quantitative descriptive research design to obtain information on the significance of Related Learning Experience to competent nursing work performance.

Research Site

The study was conducted at St. Mary's College of Baliuag, Inc., a Catholic school in City of Baliwag, Bulacan, Philippines.

Respondents

The study had 100 nursing students as respondents. They were assigned to government and private hospitals for Related Learning Experience.

Instrumentation

The respondents were purposively sampled among the undergraduate nursing students. Data were collected between August 2023 to April 2024 through an online questionnaire. These were analyzed using mean and standard deviation.

Research Ethics Protocol

This study was conducted in accordance with the guiding principles of the SMCB Research Ethics Committee. The respondents expressed their willingness to cooperate for the completion of the study through an informed consent form.

Translational Research

The findings of the study will be presented and discussed in the research forum to all the SMCB personnel for dissemination. It will also be published in the college research journal, "The Beacon Light", edition 2025, for wider information.

Results and Discussion

Results of the study revolve on areas of Clinical Efficiency, Critical Thinking, Problem-solving and Social-Moral support as provided by academically qualified, and competent clinical instructors. These are the factors contributing to creating skilled nurses who show genuine care to their patients, performing work with great efficiency, and caring with empathy and compassion.

Table 1 displays the demographic profile of the respondents.

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

	Indicators	Frequency	Percentage
Age	18 years of age	4	4.00
	19 years of age	47	47.00
	20 years of age	26	26.00
	21 years of age	13	13.00
	22 years of age	5	5.00
	23 years of age	2	2.00
	25 years of age	1	1.00
	26 years of age	1	1.00
Sex	43 years of age	1	1.00
	Male	22	22.00
	Female	78	78.00

As shown in the table, 47 (47%) of the respondents are 19 years old, 26 (26%) are 20 years old, 13 (13%) are 21 years old, five (5) or 5% are 22 years old, four (4) or 4% are 18 years old, and two (2) or 2% are 23 years old. On the other hand, the ages 25, 26 and 43 have one (1) respondent each.

Furthermore, as presented, majority of the respondents are female consisting of 78 which is

equivalent to 78 % of the total respondents while 22 or 22% of the respondents are male. Since the nursing course is basically a female dominated profession, this explains why majority of the respondents are female.

Female students choose nursing for altruistic reason since in the history of nursing during the reign of Florence Nightingale, she envisioned nursing as a profession destined for women as it

is an extension of mothering roles of nurturing, soothing and caring. (Prosen, 2022).

Table 2 shows the mean, and the standard deviation of the responses of the respondents on the questionnaire.

Table 2. Results of Related Learning Experience of Respondents on Work Performance

Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. Mastery of nursing theories is intensified through RLE.	4.71	0.61	Agree
2. Mastery of RLE is the result of comprehensive theories.	4.69	0.61	Agree
3. Mastery of nursing skills is demonstrated in the RLE.	4.79	0.56	Agree
4. RLE has an impact on student nurse's clinical performance in terms of knowledge, motivation, and clinical setting.	4.87	0.49	Agree
5. Patient experience through RLE is an essential aspect of ensuring quality healthcare for all.	4.86	0.49	Agree
6. Understanding how patients perceive their interactions with healthcare providers and facilities is attained through RLE.	4.83	0.55	Agree
7. Overall satisfaction, trust, and confidence in the student nurse's care is demonstrated during RLE.	4.82	0.54	Agree
8. Clinical experience helps student nurses become accustomed to high-stress moments.	4.77	0.60	Agree
9. RLE enables student nurses to hone their preparation skills and reflexes to ensure that they are ready for anything.	4.82	0.54	Agree
10. Comprehensive exposure to RLE enhances student nurses' ability to identify diverse patient cases.	4.76	0.61	Agree
11. The guidance and mentorship experienced during RLE prepare students to face work challenges.	4.80	0.57	Agree
12. Critical thinking and problem-solving skills developed in RLE are vital for tackling complex and critical patient's care.	4.82	0.54	Agree
13. Experience in managing stress during RLE enables students to stay calm and focused on their work.	4.75	0.61	Agree
14. Working with different patient groups in RLE enhances students' cultural understanding, preparing them for the varied scenarios they may encounter in the field.	4.84	0.51	Agree
15. Real-life situations in RLE teach students to adapt and handle unexpected challenges in patient's care.	4.84	0.53	Agree
16. RLE boost students' confidence in making clinical decisions, which is a key for working efficiently and effectively.	4.82	0.52	Agree
17. Observing an experienced RN during RLE helps students learn best practices for patient care.	4.79	0.56	Agree

Figure 1. Mean Results of Related Learning Experience of Respondents on Work Performance

Table 2 illustrates that item 4, ‘RLE has an impact on student nurse’s clinical performance in terms of knowledge, motivation, and clinical setting’, received the highest mean of 4.87 with standard deviation of 0.49, interpreted as Agree. Meanwhile, item 2, Mastery of RLE is the result of comprehensive theories. ’, obtained the lowest mean of 4.69 with standard deviation of 0.61, classified as Agree.

The findings agreed with the research done by Fadana et al. (2021) that during clinical immersion in the hospital, nursing students are confronted with dilemmas such as fear of committing mistakes in drug administration, inability to cope with patient’s demands but if they were trained with sufficient knowledge, and right motivation by their clinical instructors, coping is easier.

Conclusion

Nursing students undergoing clinical experience in different hospital settings encounter varied expectations and training. The findings of the study suggest the need for more conducive hospital environments, and close supervision of expert clinical instructors in terms of knowledge, skills and positive attitudes to improve the students’ learning experiences. This study has proven that students mostly learn in the clinical

setting through active listening to lectures, observation through skills demonstration from competent clinical instructors and the actual return demonstrations to boost their confidence and competence.

Qualified clinical instructors as mentors must be provided by the school to nursing students to maximize their knowledge, skills and attitudes as future primary health care workers. The following characteristics of good clinical instructors were recommended by the respondents of the study: (1) Kind, gentle, just in giving grades and dedicated mentors who can give rich experiential clinical experience with competence and self-confidence. (2) Clinical instructors should manifest creativity to employ diverse teaching and learning strategies to prevent student attrition.

This valuable information is necessary for school administrators in designing effective mentoring programs for nursing clinical exposure in the hospital setting. Hospitals, clinics and communities allotted for clinical immersion of the students must be well selected based on sound judgement and criteria for the maximum advantage of nursing students.

Recommendations

Based on the evaluation results of the study on the significance of the RLE towards competent nursing work performance, recommendations are the following:

- Mastery of the nursing theories must be consistently demonstrated and intensified in the Related Learning Experience (RLE).
- Since RLE has an impact on student nurses' clinical performance in terms of knowledge, motivation, and quality clinical setting, a strategic plan to enhance these features must be designed.
- To ensure quality healthcare for all patients, nursing students must be exposed more in cases where patient experience is exercised.
- Satisfaction, trust, and confidence in the student nurses' care must be demonstrated during RLE upon close supervision of their clinical instructors.
- Guidance and mentorship programs must be devised to prepare students to face the challenges of the RLE.

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